

TRICHOSCOPIC EVALUATION OF THERAPEUTIC RESPONSE TO ORAL TOFACITNIB THERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF ALOPECIA AREATA

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Abstract

Introduction: Alopecia Areata is an autoimmune disorder characterized by localized patches of hair loss to complete baldness, significantly impacting the quality of life.

Objective: To assess the efficacy of oral Tofacitinib therapy in patients with alopecia areata using SALT score and through trichoscopic parameters to quantify hair regrowth over a 16-week period.

Methods: After obtaining ethical approval, one group pretest-post-test study involving 51 patients (8 patients lost to follow-up) with alopecia areata was conducted at Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital's Dermatology Department from September 2023 to December 2024. Following Informed Consent and investigations, patients were given oral Tofacitinib (5 mg twice a day) for 16 weeks. SALT scores were recorded at baseline, week 8, and week 16 to assess clinically for efficacy. Trichoscopic evaluations were recorded at each follow-up point to assess key parameters such as black dots, yellow dots, exclamation marks, tapered hairs, and regrowing hairs. Statistical analysis was conducted using paired t-tests and correlation coefficients, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The SALT score indicated a significant reduction from baseline to week 16 (59.98 ± 24.47) vs (29.16 ± 27.13). Trichoscopic results showed: Black dots reduced by 39.2% ($p < 0.001$), Broken hairs reduced by 39.2% ($p < 0.001$) and yellow dots decreased by 43% ($p < 0.001$). Follicular unit per opening increased significantly ($p < 0.01$). Upright re-growing hairs increased by 37.3% ($p < 0.001$).

Increase in Follicular unit per opening and upright re-growing hairs support active regrowth. A strong positive correlation was found between the reduction in black dots ($r = 0.303$, $p < 0.033$), broken hairs ($r = 0.314$, $p < 0.026$) and improvement in SALT score.

Conclusion: Tofacitinib demonstrated significant clinical efficacy in improving hair regrowth. Trichoscopic evaluation provided a reliable, non-invasive method

to assess therapeutic outcomes and can help detect early signs of regrowth that might not be visible otherwise. This can reassure patients that treatment is working, encouraging them to continue their treatment.

INTRODUCTION:

Alopecia areata (AA) is an immune-mediated condition characterized by transient hair loss.(1) It is a condition marked by localized hair loss patches and anomalies in the nails.(2) A single small patch of baldness to complete baldness on the scalp, torso, eyelashes, and eyebrows are all possible as a result of AA. Almost 40% of AA patients only endure one patch and fully recover on their own within six months. While another 27% may go through additional patches but may still fully recover within a year, the remaining 33% will have a chronic form of the illness.(3)

The National Alopecia Areata Foundation guidelines recommend utilizing SALT score (Severity of alopecia tool) to assess severity of disease. Trichoscopy, in particular, aids in diagnosis by identifying certain indicators such as reduced hair count per pilosebaceous unit.(4)

Reliably effective treatment options for AA are not available yet. (2,5) Multiple JAK inhibitors are found to be effective in the treatment of Alopecia Areata with positive results in stimulating hair regrowth and improving nail degeneration(2) Tofacitinib, an oral small-molecule inhibitor works by blocking JAK-dependent cytokine signaling, leading to reduced inflammation.(6) These treatment methods have been observed to have an impact on immune response of the body, resulting in lowering NK cells and lymphocytes, along with a rise in B-cell numbers.(6)

Ibrahim et al. conducted a research which determined 53.8% of patients with Alopecia Areata have experienced a minimum of 50% hair regrowth when treated with tofacitinib.(7) A systematic review done for 14 studies that evaluated hair regrowth rates based on intensity of alopecia utilizing SALT score demonstrated that the overall rate of complete hair regrowth (SALT changes > 50%) among patients with alopecia areata who received tofacitinib was 54.0%.(8)

Trichoscopy is a practical and non-invasive method that allows for magnified images of hair as well as scalp, aiding in the diagnosis of various hair

and scalp conditions. The trichoscopic features of alopecia areata (AA) were initially described by Lacarrubba and colleagues in 2004. After that, many researches have been conducted to explore the contribution of trichoscopy in diagnosing AA, assessing disease activity, severity, prognosis, and evaluating treatment efficacy.(9) Trichoscopy has demonstrated the potential to identify early therapeutic responses that may not be clinically apparent, providing valuable insights into AA management. The current study is designed to see improvement of SALT scores in patients of AA, and, in addition, Trichoscopic evaluation will be done. Though few studies are available for oral tofacitinib in cases of AA but none of them evaluated its response with Trichoscopy. In the future it can be utilized to treat AA, and Trichoscopic evaluations can also be added for detailed evaluation.

Materials and Methods:

After taking ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board, one group pretest-post-test study was conducted at Ghurki Trust Teaching Hospital Dermatology department from September 2023 to December 2024. The study protocol followed the Declaration of Helsinki's ethical guidelines and Good Clinical Practice (GCP) guidelines. Sample size of 59 cases was calculated by WHO sample size calculator using a 90% confidence interval, 0.10 margin of error, and the anticipated percentage of patients who received a regrowth of at least 50% or greater improvement in SALT score as 32%. (10) Patients with greater than 30% Alopecia, as calculated by utilizing the SALT score, between ages of 12 and 60 years of either gender, and who have not received therapy in the past three months were included in the study. The study excluded females having pregnancy or lactating mothers, patients having an active infection at the disease location, patients receiving treatment with biological agents or immunomodulatory drugs for any systemic illness. Patients who have a history of

thromboembolic events, cardiovascular abnormalities, malignancies, acquired immunodeficiency syndrome, and patients having hypersensitivity reactions to tofacitinib were also excluded.

All patients provided written informed consent before participating in the trial. A detailed history and clinical examination including calculation of SALT SCORE was done. All patients were given oral tofacitinib 5 mg twice daily for a duration of 16 weeks, initiated only after confirmation of normal baseline investigations and a negative IGRA test. Efficacy of the drug is determined by calculating the SALT score (at baseline and 16th week) and Trichoscopic evaluation (at baseline, 8th, and 16th week) of therapy. Trichoscopic examination was done using a handheld dermoscope (Heine DELTA 30, 10 fold magnification). It involves evaluating diagnostic trichoscopic parameters, including identifying the center and hour marker (six o'clock) of the patch and then to assess various factors such as broken hairs, exclamation mark hairs, follicular units per opening, yellow dots, short vellus hairs, black dots, tapered hairs, re-growing hairs, and pigtail hairs.(9) During each follow-up, the overall improvement percentage is calculated based on the percentage of trichoscopic parameters, and a score ranging from 0 to 4 is assigned accordingly (attached-Annexure-

1). Clinical and Trichoscopic photographs were taken at baseline and each follow-up visit by a digital camera (Google Pixel 8, with a 50-megapixel-rated main rear sensor) after taking consent from the patients.

Data entry and analysis were done with SPSS version 26. Normality of data was checked by using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, which exhibited that the data were not normally distributed. Therefore, we applied non-parametric tests for analysis. To compare baseline and post-treatment SALT scores and trichoscopic parameters, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test was used. The Spearman's rank correlation was used to evaluate the correlation between SALT scores and trichoscopic features. A p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

The study included 51 patients (8 patients lost to follow-up) with a mean age of 23.66 ± 9.82 years. Females were 57.6% and males were 42.4%. Majority of patients, 41 (69.5%) had a disease duration of 6 months to 2 years. 12 patients (20.3%) had a positive family history of alopecia areata. The mean SALT score was 59.98 ± 24.47 at baseline, which reduced to 29.16 ± 27.13 by week 16, showing significant improvement. Figure 1.

Figure 1: Mean SALT score reduction after tofacitinib therapy

There was a statistically significant improvement in trichoscopic parameters at the 16th week as compared to baseline. (P<0.01) Table 1.

Strong negative correlation was found between SALT score and follicular unit per opening (r= -0.792, p< 0.001), suggesting that reduced disease

severity is associated with increased follicular activity. Furthermore, weak but statistically significant positive correlations were observed

between SALT score and black dots, broken hairs, and yellow dots, confirming their association with disease activity. Table 2.

TABLE 1: Trichoscopic data at baseline, week 8 and week 16

Parameters	Baseline n=51	8 th week n=51	16 th week n=51	P-value
Follicular-unit-per-opening				
0% in field.	4(7.8%)	1(2.0%)		
1% to 25% in field	27(53.0%)	17(33.3%)	3(5.9%)	
26% to 50% in field.	20(39.2%)	31(60.8%)	16(31.4%)	<.001
51% to 75% in field		2(3.9%)	24(47.0%)	
76% to 100% in field			8(15.7%)	
Black dots				
0% in field.	12(23.5%)	17(33.3%)	32(62.7%)	
1% to 25% in field	10(19.6%)	19(37.3%)	17(33.3%)	<.001
26% to 50% in field.	28(54.9%)	15(29.4%)	2(4.0)	
51% to 75% in field	1(2.0%)			
76% to 100% in field				
Broken Hair				
0% in field.	19(37.3%)	24(47.1%)	39(76.5%)	
1% to 25% in field	16(31.4%)	22(43.1%)	10(19.6%)	
26% to 50% in field.	16(31.4%)	5(9.8%)	2(3.9%)	<.001
51% to 75% in field				
76% to 100% in field				
Exclamation Marks				
0% in field.	23(45.1%)	31(60.8%)	45(88.2%)	
1% to 25% in field	17(33.3%)	17(33.3%)	5(9.8%)	
26% to 50% in field.	11(21.6%)	3(5.9%)	1(2.0%)	<.001
51% to 75% in field				
76% to 100% in field				

Tapered hair				
0% in field.	15(29.4%)	18(35.3%)	31(60.8%)	
1% to 25% in field	24(47.1%)	27(52.9%)	13(25.5%)	
26% to 50% in field.	12(23.5%)	6(11.8%)	5(9.8%)	<.001
51% to 75% in field			2(3.9%)	
76% to 100% in field				
Yellow dots				
0% in field.	5(9.8%)	8(15.7%)	27(52.9%)	
1% to 25% in field	15(29.4%)	15(29.4%)	21(41.2%)	
26% to 50% in field.	28(54.9%)	26(51.0%)	3(5.9%)	
51% to 75% in field	3(5.9%)	2(3.9%)		<.001
76% to 100% in field				
Short Vellus hair				
0% in field.	21(41.2%)	33(64.7%)	44(86.3%)	
1% to 25% in field	26(51.0%)	18(35.3%)	7(13.7%)	
26% to 50% in field.	4(7.8%)			<.001
51% to 75% in field				
76% to 100% in field				
Upright- re-growing hairs				
0% in field.	46(90.2%)	31(62.7%)	27(52.9%)	
1% to 25% in field	5(9.8%)	19(37.3%)	23(45.1%)	
26% to 50% in field.			1(2.0%)	
51% to 75% in field				<.001
76% to 100% in field				
Pigtail-hairs				
0% in field.	48(94.1%)	36(70.6%)	29(56.9%)	
1% to 25% in field	3(5.9%)	15(29.4%)	22(43.1%)	

26% to 50% in field.				<.001
51% to 75% in field				
76% to 100% in field				

TABLE 2: Correlation between SALT score and trichoscopic features

SALT Score	Follicular unit per opening	Black dots	Broken Hair	Exclamation Marks	Tapered hair	Yellow dots	Vellus hair	Upright-regrowing-hairs	Pigtail-hairs
r	-0.792	.303	.314	.069	.248	.317	.174	-.095	-.001
p-value	.000	.033	.026	.634	.082	.025	.227	.512	.992

Figure 2: Trichoscopy at baseline showing yellow dots, and after 16 weeks, there is a complete absence of yellow dots.

Figure 3: Trichoscopy at baseline showing exclamation mark hairs and black dots, and after 16 weeks, these features are absent.

Figure 4: Trichoscopy at baseline showing exclamation mark hairs and broken hairs, and after 16 weeks, these features are absent.

Figure 5: Trichoscopy at baseline showing pigtail hairs and after tofacitinib therapy there is absence of this feature.

Discussion:

Alopecia areata (AA) is an autoimmune disorder that causes non-scarring hair loss, driven by attack of hair follicles. (8,11) Activation of Th1, Th17 and Th2 cytokines trigger this immune attack. Th17 (IL17E and IL17) and Th1 cytokines (TNF, IL-2, IL-12) also correlate with disease activity. (12,13) Tofacitinib is small molecule JAK1 and JAK3 inhibitor. Normal cell growth, immunoregulation and cytokine regulation are

modulated by JAK signaling pathway. (6) In a meta-analysis, the pooled complete hair regrowth rate was reported in 54.0% of patients treated with Tofacitinib (8). The results of our study are in line with previous research, demonstrating significant improvement of 51.4% in SALT scores with tofacitinib therapy. This was similar to outcomes reported by Sharath, Jabbari, and others, where significant percentage of patients attained complete hair regrowth. (5,7,8,14-16) Table 3

STUDY	Our study	Sharath et al. (14)	Jabbari et al. (15)	Ibrahim et al. (7)	Liu et al. (5)	Criaglow et al. (16)
SALT IMPROVEMENT	51.4%	91.3%	56.8%	50.5%	64.7%	61.0%

Table 4: Comparison of Trichoscopic Findings across various Studies at Baseline

Trichoscopic Findings	Our Study	Al-Dhubaibi et al. (pooled prevalence) (17)	Ganjoo et al. (18)	Bains et al. (19)	Inui et al. (20)	Waskiel et al. (21)	Bapu et al. (22)
Yellow dots (%)	90.2%	61.0%	95.7%	61.5%	63.7%	62%	89.6%
Broken Hairs (%)	62.8%	40.0%	81.4%	69.2%	45.7%	49%	12.9%
Black dots (%)	76.5%	56.0%	84.2%	82.7%	80.4%	53%	78.4%
Tapered Hairs (%)	70.6%	35.0%	22.8%	9.6%	31.7%	51%	12.1%
Short Vellus Hairs (%)	58.8%	46.0%	74.2%	57.7%	72.7%	61%	78.4%
Upright Regrowing Hairs (%)	9.8%					23%	
Pigtail Hairs (%)	5.9%			28.8%		21%	6.9%

Among trichoscopic findings, our study found yellow dots most sensitive marker of Alopecia areata which is in concordance with various studies (18,20–28). The high prevalence of yellow dots was observed in phototype V in accordance with Fitzpatrick’s scale.(21) Whereas some other studies showed black dots as the most sensitive finding. (9,19) Yellow dots are present mostly in inactive, chronic form of alopecia areata. (21,29,30) Our study also demonstrated that Yellow dots were less responsive to treatment, which is in line with other studies. (18,20,31)

The present study demonstrates that there was a marked reduction of dystrophic hair shaft features i.e. Broken hairs, Exclamation marks, Black dots after Tofacitinib therapy which is in comparison with study by Sharath et al.(14) Table 4. There was positive correlation of Broken hairs and Black dots with disease activity in our study which is consistent with previous studies.(17,28,31–34) Likewise, Vijay et al. described that in AA, black dots, yellow dots, tapering hairs and broken hairs positively correlate with disease activity. (35)

Another study highlighted that in AA, black dots, broken hairs, tapering hairs and short vellus hairs indicate disease activity. (20)

In our study, short vellus hairs were decreased after tofacitinib therapy, which is also reported by previous studies. (14) Burnat et al. observed that short vellus hairs are replaced by terminal hairs in the remission phase. (31) Lacarrubba et al. noted two forms of hair regrowth in patients with chronic AA. The first pattern was uniform and reflected early disease remission i.e. upright regrowing hairs, and the second pattern was twisted vellus hair i.e., pigtail hair regrowth, which is in concordance with our study, which showed 47.1% improvement in upright re-growing hairs and 43.1% increase in pigtail hairs. (36) Features like tapering distal end and upright positioning, if present in re-growing hairs, then they are known as upright regrowing hairs. They must be differentiated from short vellus hairs.(37,38) So, pigtail hairs and upright re-growing hairs are positive predictors for hair re-growth, while broken hairs, black dots, tapered hairs, and

exclamation mark hairs are negative predictive markers.(31)

This study has some limitations. The single-center setting, reduced sample size, and absence of a reference arm limit the applicability of results. Brief follow-up period and potential evaluator bias in trichoscopic assessment can also affect the outcomes.

Trichoscopy is a non-invasive, reliable tool for establishing diagnosis as well as monitoring of therapeutic response to treatment. Short vellus hairs and yellow dots are the most sensitive features. On the other hand, tapering hairs and black dots are the most specific features of AA. Diagnosis depends on the recognition of a collection of characteristic findings rather than the appearance of a single trichoscopic feature. Diagnostic accuracy of AA and evaluation of its treatment response can be enhanced by utilizing trichoscopy in our routine clinical practice.

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